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ENGL 134

21 November 2021

Mass Incarceration: The Freedom Struggle

Since the 1970's, mass incarceration in the United States has seen extraordinary growth and continues to increase and harm people to this day. Despite only having 5% of the world's population, the U.S holds 25% of the world's prisoners, disproportionately incarcerating people of color. Rather than allowing individuals to rehabilitate and become better, our Justice System significantly diminishes the quality of one's life both in and out of jail, which leads many to an endless cycle of imprisonment and crime. Historically, law enforcement has targeted African Americans and made accusations against them, leading to a large amount of incarceration among them (Taylor 201). By increasing the police presence in black and minority neighborhoods, rather than having more security and safety, there is more police surveillance and arrests of even the smallest crimes (Taylor 202). Minority groups are disproportionately arrested for small, petty crimes which do not pose a real threat to society but keep them in the loop of incarceration. Racial bias creates an increasingly alarming U.S incarceration rate that disproportionately affects minority groups without the regard of "justice for all".

Historically, the U.S has used several different strategies and tactics to oppress minorities like Black and Hispanic people. Through tactics like over policing, we have found new ways of oppressing minorities which on the surface seem like they would do more good for the community, but in reality does more harm. Over-Policing significantly increases police presence in disadvantaged neighborhoods and though we typically would think that it would help the

community, it actually creates more problems and harm because, “police officers view African Americans as criminals and in need of police surveillance” (Taylor 202). This means that instead of offering services and protection to those in these disadvantaged neighborhoods, they target and arrest them for even the smallest of actions/crimes, feeding into mass incarceration. It is stated that, “Mass incarceration are not simply collateral consequences for individuals but are borne collectively, most notably by African Americans living in acutely disadvantaged communities that experience high levels of policing and surveillance” (Gutierrez and Pettit). Over-policing creates a bias stereotype that particular minority groups need to constantly be under police surveillance, which only reinforces a superficial bias that minority men are more dangerous and criminal.

This issue has especially prevailed in recent years. Take George Floyd for instance; after paying with what was thought to be a counterfeit \$20 bill at a local convenience store, he was approached by police and negatively profiled, ultimately leading to his murder in the name of “justice.” This demonstrates how a small crime like paying with a counterfeit bill, can have fatal effects on people of color in over-policed areas. “Police–black community relations have been a persistent issue in the black freedom struggle... African Americans and the U.S. criminal justice system have had an adversarial relationship for well over a century, and it persists into the 21st century with the continuing “blight” of mass black incarceration” (Taylor 201). This is important because by throwing more and more people into prison for small, non-violent crimes, we not only take away some of their rights, but also change the whole trajectory of their lives because of the victimization, trauma, and abuse that most people undergo in prison. “Research has shown that spending time in prison has negative effects on 1) employment, earnings, and wage growth; 2) political engagement; and 3) health and well-being” (Gutierrez and Pettit). The U.S Justice

System does not truly serve “justice” if there is no way to escape the endless cycle of racially biased crime.

As a result of over-policing in lower-socioeconomic neighborhoods, we not only see the obvious increase of people being incarcerated, but also, we see that for these less serious crimes racial disparity increases, whereas for more serious violent crimes the racial disparity is modest (Crutchfield and Weeks 47). Meaning that for smaller crimes, like drug possession or petty theft, a person of color is much more likely to be sent to prison, than someone who is White. They state, “Good evidence indicates that racial and ethnic groups use and sell drugs proportionally to their representation in the population... But, more than 50 percent of those imprisoned for drug sales or possession are people of color” (Crutchfield and Weeks 47). This demonstrates how despite the proportionality seen amongst each race in selling/possessing drugs, a black man is still up to 13 times more likely to be sentenced on drug charges than a white man (Crutchfield and Weeks 47). This matters because not only are those directly being put into prison affected by the mass incarceration, but also children and families. According to a source, “financial obligations associated with criminal convictions, transferred to family members, can fuel a cycle of debt and obligation that spans across generations” (Gutierrez and Pettit). The impact of being incarcerated goes beyond just that one person and also has negative effects on everyone around them, which has the power to impact the generations to come.

However, like any issue, there are limitations. Some scholars may argue that because implicit bias training does not have a tangible effect on law enforcement behavior, there is not a pervasive issue that needs rectifying. In a 2020 study conducted by the NYPD on behavior before and after racial-bias training, we see that post-training enforcement behavior is similar to pre-training behavior. For instance, prior to training, enforcement actions involving black people,

such as arrests were 47% and after training it was 48% (Kaste). The lead author of the study, Robert E. Worden says, “It’s fair to say that we could not detect effects of the training on officers’ enforcement behaviors,” (Kaste). These results indicate that not only were there no positive changes made amongst law enforcement behaviors, but there was actually a slight increase in not just arrests, but also stops and frisks (Kaste). Additionally, many may argue that these implicit bias training do not have much of an effect on law enforcement, and that these funds can be allocated elsewhere to support the community. According to Tucker, a deputy commissioner, “it’s worth the \$5.5 million it cost to train the department’s 36,000 officers,” (Kaste). For a training that has little to no effect on enforcement law behavior, that \$5.5 million dollars that could go towards community resources or other police programs, is somewhat wasted. However, the results from the training are null, and according to Worden, “it doesn’t prove implicit bias training changes cops’ behavior, but it doesn’t disprove it either,” (Kaste). By continuing this tough on crime mentality, where we continuously imprison people for small mistakes, we can expect to see more money being put towards creating new prisons, rather than for communities in need and other critical programs that need budgeting.

Nevertheless, there is evidence proving that racial prejudice plays a large part in punishment preferences among white people (Nellis). Not only that, but, “when individuals—practitioners in particular—are made consciously aware of their bias through implicit bias training, diversification of the workforce, and education on the important differences between implicit and explicit bias, this can mitigate or even erase the actions they would otherwise take based on unexplored assumptions” (Nellis). In another study conducted by the NYPD, we see how the thoughts of law enforcement have changed post-training. For instance, the survey asked, ‘Implicit biases may lead officers to be over vigilant- that is, act

aggressively when someone is not a threat,' where prior to training 8% strongly agreed and 28% somewhat agreed. However, after training we see that now, 15% of those in law enforcement strongly agree with the statement, and 39% somewhat agree (Kaste). Clearly, implicit bias training not only educates its participants on biases, but also provides strategies like raising awareness, routine monitoring, and identifying triggers, that can be applied to daily life and encourage compassion/empathy.

In order to work towards improving mass incarceration in America, we must diminish the racial biases which lie within our justice system, by calling on government officials to implement more just laws and resources into communities which need the support. Diminishing racial bias starts and ends with us, the average American. Through protests and petitions we can bring more light and attention to these issues, and create a conversation about what needs to be done both in the government and in regular day to day life to create a more just and equal society where the era of mass incarceration in the United States can begin to lessen at last. Furthermore, by terminating society's use of prisons to confront social problems, we can work towards reducing the effects of the consequences from being imprisoned, on minority groups (Cruthfield and Weeks 51). Once united, communities can begin to see real change. Having an increased presence of both mothers and fathers in homes, will significantly improve behavior and over-all lifestyle from a young age, and reduce the amount of mental health issues amongst children, leading to an overall happier life and community. As Malcolm X once said, "Our unity shocked them and we should continue to shock the white man by working together."

Works Cited

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Reflection

1. Specifically walk me through the evolution of your project; what are two sources that challenged your initial impression of the topic? How did the research process help you develop your ideas?

One source that challenged my initial impression on mass incarceration was “NYPD Study: Implicit Bias Training Changes Minds, Not Necessarily Behavior.” At first I thought that the officers would go into the training with some biases, but data showed that to not be true. It was really interesting to see that for most officers, having programs like implicit bias training had little to no effect on their behavior towards others, but more specifically people of color. This article helped to develop my ideas on my counterclaim because it allowed me to see opposing ideas/views by challenging my initial impression on the subject. Another source that challenged my initial impression on mass incarceration was, “The Effects of Mass Incarceration on Communities of Color.” Though I knew that people of color were disproportionately incarcerated, it was interesting to read more about how racial disparity increases amongst smaller crime statistics, but it is modest for more severe crimes.

2. Describe one of your **process artifacts** and explain how it shows evidence of your progress towards one of the following course learning outcomes: ****remember a process artifact is any one piece of work that is a part of your writing process; it can be a piece of formal or informal writing etc****

I think that the process artifact which helped me most during this writing process was my research outline. I started off with an outline that was a bit all over the place but after getting some peer review I was able to mix things up and move parts around to make my essay flow

better. For instance, I initially had a phrase under “identify your argument” but discovered that it would work better as my call to action towards the end of my paper because it talks about what the average person can/should do to help. Additionally, once I got more eyes on my paper, I was able to further develop a counterclaim which would not significantly diminish my argument. Rather than a counter argument that would be hard to attain like “Prison’s exist solely to protect society,” I developed a counterclaim that is more attainable, stating, “implicit bias training does not have a tangible effect on law enforcement behavior, there is not a pervasive issue that needs rectifying”

3. Describe how you integrated one source into your essay. Where did you quote or paraphrase the source? How did you use it to help you make a point in your own argument?

For my first source in paragraph one that was used by Clarence Taylor, rather than using quotes or formally introducing the author, I summed up his ideas and cited him at the end of each sentence, after each idea. I think that this helps to strengthen my ideas because instead of just putting the author's words in quotes, I shorten the author’s idea and only pull out the main ideas or what gets the point across best.

4. What is the strongest paragraph in your final draft and why? What is the weakest paragraph; specifically where in that paragraph do you feel you could have added more revision and what would that revision look like?

I think that my strongest paragraph is paragraph 4 because I start with the problem and its causes, then provide a quote by a scholarly source to strengthen my argument. Additionally, after my commentary for the quote, I state why this matters and who it is directly affecting.

I think that my weakest paragraph is the following paragraph (5). I had some trouble with developing a counterargument, and feel like I could have gone more in depth. For instance, towards the end of the paragraph I wish I could have talked more about reallocating the money and what exactly that looks like.